

Impact of Work from Home among Teachers during the COVID-19 Pandemic: A Case Study

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Abstract: This study utilized a single case study design to describe the impact of Work from Home (WFH) alternative work arrangement among the five grade chairpersons of Saavedra Saway Central Elementary School for the School-Year 2020-2021. This study used the key participant interview approach to gather the needed data. Findings of the study revealed the case of the five teachers of Saavedra Saway Central Elementary School and their perspective on the impact of work from home among teachers as the challenge of connectivity, ups and downs of productivity, and two sides of job satisfaction. The study implied that the impact of work from home among teachers entails a new challenge for teaching productivity and teaching satisfaction in the new normal educational setting. Working from home during the Covid-19 pandemic entails that a teacher should be flexible and is professional enough to adapt to the fast-changing educational landscape.

Keywords: impact, work from home, Covid-19 pandemic, public elementary school teachers, case study, Philippines.

1. INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic affects every aspect of life. It gave rise to problems throughout the country. This pandemic greatly influenced public education. The limited number of studies about the impact of work from home among teachers in public schools contributed to the vague understanding of teachers' well-being during this health crisis. The health threats posed by the Coronavirus made a sudden change in the present educational landscape. Educators innovated a new teaching mode of delivery to continue pupils' learning in public schools. Work from home among teachers was an essential move by the Department of Education curriculum planners and officials. This ensures that quality education is delivered to Filipino learners in times and situations like the Covid-19 pandemic. The Profound impact of work from home among employees, especially teachers, are arising. Studies are insufficient regarding the effects of work from home among teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic, especially those teachers who have issues regarding child care since all schools are forced to close their doors for face-to-face learning when the COVID-19 pandemic has taken place a swing. The Philippine Department of Education issued the work from a home memorandum dated June 22, 2020, which reminded all agencies to strive for the continuity of essential education services, stating that the department remains committed to protecting all personnel's health and safety. Many teachers experienced working from home for the first time, and many challenges have ascended.

Stories of hardships and challenges are heard and shared by teachers during these uncertain times. The impact of work from home among freelance writers has been explored and found out that the productivity increased among the participants, yet they voice out the dangers of the web in their data. It further confirms that at the height of the Covid-19 pandemic, as companies turned to work from home, the participants managed their time efficiently. Still, the cost of electricity and the internet adds a burden to the participants. While some of the studies conducted claim that working from home increases the employees' productivity, other studies have found the opposite. Numerous studies were conducted regarding employees working from home and obtained their experiences and perceptions. Still, little attention has been given to the impact of working from home among teachers in public schools during the Covid-19 pandemic. To conduct

this recent study is an urgent issue since the Covid-19 pandemic is still hampering every way of Filipino life. With that, the researcher develops an interest to capture the cases of these teachers working at home and contribute to understanding the impact of the alternative work arrangement to fill this research gap (Rupietta, K. & Beckmann, M., 2016; Bloom, N., Bunn, P., Mizen, P., Smietanka, P. & Thwaites, G., 2020; Mustajab, D., Bauw, A., Rasyid, Irwan, A., Akbar, M. A. & Hamid, M. A., 2020; Turkmenoğlu, G., Ulukok, E., Dogan, I., & Akin, A., 2020; Dr. Charumati, D. & Ragavi, G. 2021).

Thus, the study would like to describe and analyze the impact of work from home among the five teachers of Saavedra Saway Central Elementary School, Labangal District, Division of General Santos for the School-Year 2020-2021.

Statement of the Problem

The study aimed to describe and provide an in-depth understanding of the impact of work from home among Saavedra Saway Central Elementary School teachers for 2020-2021 during the COVID-19 pandemic. There is a need for an in-depth understanding of working from home and its impact among our public-school teachers to address the new normal public education problems during the Covid-19 pandemic.

Purpose of the Statement

This study focused only on the in-depth understanding of the impact of work from home among teachers of Saavedra Saway Central Elementary School, Labangal District, Division of General Santos for the School-Year 2020-2021. The selection process of participants of the study utilized inclusion criteria. This study was limited to the case of five public school teachers of Saavedra Saway Central Elementary School within their own experiences; thus, the generalization of the impact of work from home to other teachers of some other schools is not applicable in this study. The personal in-depth interviews were conducted at home among key participants to get the necessary information to prevent biases. The researcher ensured that the participants answered all questions thoroughly during the discussion. The Department of Education has set guidelines for the alternative work arrangement of teachers in times of the Covid-19 pandemic. Thus, the study aimed to describe and understand the impact of work from home among teachers.

Research Questions

This study sought to answer the following questions:

1. How do participants describe the impact of working from home among teachers during the COVID- 19 pandemic?
 - 1.1 How do participants view the impact of work from home during the COVID-19 pandemic?
 - 1.2 How do participants feel about the impact of working from home during the COVID19 pandemic?
 - 1.3 How does working from home during the COVID-19 pandemic affect the teachers?

Theoretical Lens

This study was anchored on the advanced social learning theory. The Theory of Behavior states that the idea of learning is a function of behavior change. Noam Chomsky's language acquisition theory also supports this. In this theory, the social environment and individual personality created probabilities of behavior, and the reinforcement of these behaviors led to learning. Social learning theory emphasized the subjective nature of the responses and effectiveness of reinforcement types (Rotter, J. B., 2015; Bandura, A., 2016; Skinner, 2007 cited by Schulltz, D. P., Schultz, S.E., 2016).

The main idea in social learning theory is that personality represents an interaction of the individual with their environment. There is no such thing as an internal personality unrelated to the domain. Neither can one consider conducting an automated reaction to a set of objective environmental cues. Instead, to understand behavior, one must take into account both the personal history of learning and experiences and the environmental triggers that the person is aware of and respond to. Bandura's theory describes personality as a relatively stable set of potentials for responding to situations in a particular way. This theory resonates deeply with the researcher as it represents the power of phenomenological inquiry to light the social learning and the impact of work from home among public school teachers and the new typical teaching environment. As a public-school teacher who had personally experienced work from home, the researcher attempted to follow Bandura's theory to leave her research question in the presence of other teachers.

The uncertainties of the school year amidst the Covid-19 pandemic have illuminated her research interest, as she sought to understand more fully the impact of work from home from the experience of other teachers. Rotter's theory sees personality, and therefore behavior, as constantly unpredictable. Change the way the person contemplates or change the

environment the person responds to so the behavior will change. A researcher optimistically conceives people. They are being drawn forward by their goals, seeking to maximize their reinforcement rather than just avoiding punishment.

Meanwhile, another study states that “Phenomenological research in social learning is done with an eye to the consequences for action.” Hence, the researcher sought to understand social learning to act more thoughtfully in the impact of work from home from teachers’ lives as they continue in their pedagogical journeys in public schools (Barritt, 2014; Rotter, J. B., 2015; Leary, M. R., 2019; Trip, S., Bora, C. H., Marian, M., Halmajan, A., & Drugas, M. I., 2019).

The researcher’s journey toward understanding the world in which she lives and works also led her to the phenomenological light that can powerfully uncover the lived experience of other teachers. Language Acquisition Theory supports this. It proposed that “human beings are somehow specifically built to” grasp and acquire language and that this is due to a specific yet undiscovered cognitive process. The researcher is fortunate to occupy the same environment and language as public-school educators. Thankful that she may be able to shine the light of social learning on their daily work to understand the impact of the working environment from lived experiences of others (Chomsky, N., 2012 cited by Johnson, K., 2017).

The researcher felt grounded in a theory that could bring light to the impact of teaching environment-alternative work arrangement of teachers during these dark times, which she observed had struggled to find their place in an ever-increasing dynamic world of education. Social learning theory can clarify the impact of work from home among teachers. They seek tact and understanding in the complex technical world of policy mandates and the interpersonal relationships they find when immersed in the public school system during the Covid-19 pandemic.

2. METHODOLOGY

Sample and Site

The participants of this study were the public school teachers of Saavedra Saway Central Elementary School, Labangal District, Division of General Santos for the School Year 2020-2021. The selection of participants utilized purposive sampling and inclusion criteria.

The participants were five (5) regular teaching personnel who are elementary school teachers. Inclusion criteria are as follows: All respondents must be teachers in a modular distance learning platform. All respondents had experienced challenges with alternative work arrangements in modular distance learning. All participants are elementary classroom teachers with a permanent appointment in the Department of Education.

The in-depth interview participants comprised five (5) females whom the researcher chose through purposive sampling. The purposive sampling technique, also called judgment sampling, is a nonrandom technique that does not need underlying theories or a set number of informants—all of the participants were selected according to their willingness to become part of the study.

The participants/informants of the study were selected through homogenous sampling. This purposive sampling technique captured various perspectives relating to the researcher’s study interest. This is a non-probability sampling method, and it occurs when elements selected for the sample are chosen by the researcher’s judgment. Researchers frequently feel that they can produce a representative sample and save time and money by applying excellent decision. This sampling is suitable for qualitative studies where the researcher is interested in informants who have the best knowledge concerning the research topic. Thus, the researcher decides their needed data and sets out to find people who can and are willing to give the information by knowledge or experience. (Creswell, J.W., 2015; Black, L., 2016).

The inclusion criteria used to select the teacher-participants in the study were that the participant must be a public school teacher with a permanent appointment in the Department of Education. The participant must have an approved work from home class schedule in modular distance learning. The participant must be available, willing to participate, and interested in the research undertakings.

The study was conducted in Saavedra Saway Central Elementary School. The teachers at the locale of the study have been concerned with their work from home schedule and the needs in the implementation of the modular distance learning platform. The present teaching-learning situation and the alternative work arrangement have pressed challenges for teachers, students, and parents. The researcher considered it imperative to examine the impact of work from home among teachers and how it interweaves with pupils’ academic performance during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Researcher's Role and Potential Ethical Issues

As an educator for several years, it is a fact that to stay in the profession, one has to survive all the difficulties like making lesson plans, test plans, and preparing instructional materials appropriate for the lessons one has planned for the day. The challenge of working from home in the new learning platforms during the COVID-19 pandemic may pose new ordeals in addition to the responsibilities of a teacher. The researcher is an insider in the participant's school; still, proper coordination was done in gaining access to the participants before the conduct of the study. Permission and consent letter was disseminated to the participants to achieve their approval to be the research informants.

A copy of consent was given to all the participants at the time of the interview. The interview was conducted at the participants' most preferable and convenient time. The participants were given a chance to read and explain information from the consent, including the study's objectives and procedure. The researcher made it clear that the participants could decline to participate in the study at any time to make it clear that the participation is voluntary. The researcher should ask each participant to allow videotape recordings of the interview so that the data analysis would become more credible. This strategy would reduce the risk that conclusions would reflect the systematic biases. The researcher ensured that all the information given by the participants was treated as confidential and private. The researcher maintained the anonymity of the participants by giving false names or pseudonyms. This helped safeguard the questionnaire's public opinions while protecting the participants' identities. The researcher gave an assurance to the participants that their statements are going to be confidential. Aside from the verbal oath of confidentiality, they also signed an agreement that their statements will be used for the study only. Honesty plays a vital role in this research study thus; the researcher reported and transcribed information accordingly to gain the participants' confidence. This is a way of building rapport and gaining the participants' trust. In analyzing data, taking sides with the participants was avoided and positive and negative information was reported. Careless errors and negligence were avoided and a record and a copy of every detail in the research were kept to assure credible details. Like the audio recordings, the gathered data was then carefully kept but deleted at the end of the study to conform to the Data Privacy Act in research studies. Lastly, the researcher collated the needed data for the study and did the data analysis. Thematic analysis was used.

Data Gathering Strategies

The data were gathered using an in-depth interview method, following the steps in qualitative inquiry. Prior to the interview, the researcher prepared the interview guide questions. These questions underwent validation by three experts in qualitative research studies. The researcher prepared several leading questions for the participants to answer. The personal interview method allowed the researcher to probe and expand the interviewee's response. (Creswell, J. W., 2015).

An in-depth interview guide was utilized to facilitate an in-depth understanding of the teacher's perception of the impact of work from home in their daily lives. This prepared interview guide was used to ensure that the same information would be obtained from each informant. Then a face-to-face interview was done, and participants were encouraged to talk freely and tell their stories using their own words. At the end of each interview, the researcher reminded the participants about the need for a follow-up with them through phone calls to discuss the study's findings and ensure that the results reflect their own experiences. The researcher asked for the consent of the participants to allow the recording of the in-depth interview with audiotape to become reliable. To auditorily document the conversation of all five (5) participants, the researcher used a voice recorder during the interview for a more accessible analysis. Then, the recorded conversations were manually transcribed using a computer for written documentation. After transcription, the respondents confirmed this to authenticate the truthfulness of the data gathered.

Validation

The researcher asked for approval from the three experts in qualitative studies. They checked and validated the research instrument, particularly the interview guide questions. The researcher considered any suggestions and recommendations provided by them. This method ensured that the interview questions captured the impact of work from home as perceived by teachers. The researcher followed the ethical procedures required by Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges. All questions included in the interview guide led to the description and understanding of the impact of work from home among public school teachers.

Data Analysis Approach

When conducting a qualitative study, the researcher tried to get as close as possible to the participants being studied to minimize the distance between themselves. The experts pointed out that the data analysis in a research study involves summarizing the mass of data collected and presenting the results to communicate the essential features. Data will be analyzed using a method that includes data reduction, data display, conclusion, drawing, and verification, adding that qualitative content analysis is “any qualitative material and attempts to identify core consistencies and meanings” (Creswell, J. W., 2015; Hancock, J., Ockleford, R., and Windridge, N., 2017). The following steps represent the Colaizzi process for phenomenological data analysis. (Morrow, T., Rodriguez, H., and King, J., 2015). The first step is to read the transcript multiple times to obtain a general sense of the whole content. The second step is extracting significant statements that pertain to the phenomenon under study. These important statements should be recorded on a separate sheet noting their page and lines numbers. The third step is formulating the meanings of significant statements. The researcher “bracketed” their pre-suppositions to stick closely to the phenomenon as experienced. The fourth step is to sort the formulated meanings into categories, clusters of themes, and themes. The bracketing of pre-suppositions is crucial to avoid any potential influence of existing theory. The fifth step is integrating the study's findings into a detailed description of the phenomenon under investigation. The detailed description will be presented as a narrative account. The researcher incorporated the emergent themes, theme clusters, and formulated meanings into the description to create the overall structure and ensure that the study contains experience elements. The sixth step is describing the fundamental structure of the phenomenon. Finally, the research participants should validate the findings to compare their descriptive results with their experiences. The researcher will ask the participants whether it captures their experience. The researcher may go back and modify earlier steps in the analysis in light of this feedback.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This qualitative research describes the impact of work from home among teachers in Saavedra Saway Central Elementary School, Labangal District, Division of General Santos City and is categorized into three main themes: The Challenge of Connectivity, The Ups and Down of Productivity, and The Two-sides of Teaching Satisfaction.

Main Theme: The Challenge of Connectivity

The researcher conducted an in-depth interview among five (5) Saavedra Saway Central Elementary School teachers to gather the data needed to describe the impact of work from home among teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic and out of their responses, this main theme The Challenge of Connectivity came out.

Web Accessibility

Teachers' work-from-home arrangement voiced out the need for internet connectivity to achieve their tasks effectively. COVID-19 has pushed school districts, instructors, students, and families to adapt to online instruction swiftly. Although many school districts offer blended or online learning programs, for the more than 9 million kids who do not have access to the Internet at home, these learning alternatives are lost when schools close. Thus, lack of access to fast, affordable, and reliable internet connections hinders the process of online learning. (Medina, R., 2019; Adnan, M., & Anwar, K., 2020; Chandra, S., Chang, A., Day, L., Fazlullah, A., Liu, J., McBride, L., & Weiss, D., 2020; Drane, C., Vernon, L., & O'Shea, S., 2020; Sethi, G. K., & Saini, N. K., 2020). This requires teaching skills at another level to meet the challenge head-on. This requires specialized content knowledge, teaching-learning methods, and ICT-based skills and welcome technological tools at home. During the pandemic, the country has witnessed many ICT-driven initiatives on national, local, and individual levels. There has been a practical approach in the education sector to utilize the maximum potential of technology to reach every learner and accomplish tasks while working from home. Meetings, gatherings, and seminars have been going on through virtual communities like webinars and online discussions. Teachers find ways and develop abilities to sustain continued operation via remote meetings. Though many are still trying to cope with the new normal setup in education, still, it is necessary to understand. However, it is the lack of skills that should be seen not only as a challenge but also as a chance for providing better professional development during these uncertain times. (Ballesteros, H., and Ocampo, K., 2016; Pouliakas, K., & Branka, J., 2020; Choi, L., & Chung, S., 2021; Pradhan, P., Subedi, D. R., Khatiwada, D., Joshi, K. K., Kafle, S., Chhetri, R. P., & Bhujju, D. R., 2021; Sharma, A., 2021; Subedi, D. R., Khatiwada, D., Joshi, K. K., Kafle, S., Chhetri, R. P. & Bhujju, D. R., 2021; Hylén, J., 2021). It is vital that school districts address these connectivity challenges so that students can continue learning alongside their peers, and teachers can function effectively even during their alternative work arrangement such as Work from Home (WFH) (Department of Education, 2020). This is evident in the verbatim accounts of the participant as follows:

“What I can say is our internet connection is really our challenge because we tend to connect with our learners through messenger for atleast we can contribute something to their learning but this is being hindered by our slow internet connection. Through video calling using facebook messenger it feels like we are having conversation with our learners just like we used to do during face-to-face classes but this is being interrupted by slow or poor internet connection. - Participant 1, lines 159-167

“in doing works at home, I make sure I am always connected in the internet because it is the demand of our work to be always on call especially when there are many reports to do or submit and I always make sure that my cellphone is always reachable” - Participant 2, lines 310-313

“when your internet is not stable and you have webinars or things and reports that you have to submit through email, it cause stress when you are not connected online or you have poor internet signal.” - Participant 2, lines 323-326

Flexibility

Alternative Work Arrangement was identified by the Civil Service Commission to government agencies such as DepEd to adopt individually or in combination during the period of National Emergency due to COVID-19 pandemic. In its implementation, the Department of Education personnel shall continue the strict observance of applicable health measures and the continuity of DepEd essential services and priority programs while observing the required health standards. Department of Education (2020). Teachers with excitement and hesitation received the implementation of work from home, as evident on one of the participants account:

“ahh.. in my.. in my own impression, when we say work from home refers to ahh you have to work ahh at home, not to bring, as for me I have to bring my paper works, do it at home, prepare all the things to be submitted in school and all that should be done is at home”.) - Participant 1, lines 6-9

“Actually at first at the beginning, I am excited to start my work but I realized ahh, especially now that working from home is not that very easy because there are some distractions like doing, like I am thinking of doing some household chores or I am tempted to watch television or sometimes I am lazy to do my.. my task because the environment is very different from the normal days when there’s no pandemic.”- Participant 2, lines 291-296

“at first I was hesitant because it was just like any ordinary day, like in face-to-face class. On my first day, I just did my daily routine, preparing myself physically and emotionally. - Participant 5, lines 823-825

Table 1

The Thematic Analysis of the participant's view of the impact of work from home during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Main Theme: The Challenge of Connectivity

Cluster Themes		Emergent Themes
1.	Online connectivity	1. Web accessibility
2.	Physical isolation	
3.	Varied learning platform	
4.	Weekly Home Learning Plan	
5.	Teaching using an online platform	
6.	Online reporting and evaluation	
7.	Flexible work hours	2. Flexibility
8.	Home environment	
9.	Enhance work objectives	
10.	Setting up workplace at home	
11.	Family-oriented work and adjustment	

Main Theme: The Ups and Downs of Productivity

Negative Feelings

Many teachers are worried when asked to work from home. It was found that teachers do not feel comfortable preparing lesson objectives and paperworks while tending to their children and doing household chores. According to previous studies, teachers who work from home could not get administrative support during the work-from-home setup. Teachers are emotionally tired during working from home, their job satisfaction decreased, they were stressed, they had low motivation, and they had to balance concerns between home and work. Other determinants such as personal characteristics, traits, stress factors, spouse support, and work-family or family-work conflict also influence the work satisfaction and emotional health indices. These findings consistently state that work from home is challenging for teachers because of their pre-pandemic experiences and routines. Further, working from home in many views represents a more demanding teaching situation, and special attention should be given. Teachers need to use time wisely and efficiently to keep track of the latest advances in technology and at the same time become more productive and creative in the teaching-learning process while staying healthy and happy (Cerna, A., 2016; Medina, R., 2019; Bautista, S., 2020; Cardel, M. I., Dean & Montoya-Williams, D., 2020; Criffield, A., Kracl, C., McKelvey, M., Obasi, S., & Vu, P., 2020; Lopez-Leon, S., Forero, D. & Ruiz-Díaz, P., 2020; Fodor, E., Gregor, A., Koltai, J., & Kováts, E., 2021; Ghazi-Saidi, L., Lopez, S., Bruun, G., Mader, M., & Reardon, R., 2021; Burke, R., & Greenglass, E., 1993 as cited by Krukowski, R., Jagsi, R., & Cardel, M. 2021; Kara, S., Günes, D. Z., & Tüysüzer, B. S., 2021; Krukowski, R., Jagsi, R., & Cardel, M., 2021; Kara, S., Günes, D. Z., & Tüysüzer, B. S., 2021).

“Honestly, I have to tell you frankly that it’s merely a burden for me because I’m not used to it.” - Participant 1, lines 15-16

“Yes, it’s a burden, a significant burden in the sense that you are at home and you have no one to ask for technical assistance, you have to work alone. It gives me stress because it’s a little bit different type of situation working at home.” - Participant 1, lines 42-44

“You are being affected by these emotions, the burden of your work, you are stress asking yourself if you can do your work at home alone. As a teacher you know that you can accomplish your task, yet if you are at home you can see that it is a different scene, than reporting physically at school. You ask yourself if you can do it, then you think that it’s your work. - Participant 1, lines 63-67

Positive Feelings

Participants also expressed positive remarks about working from home during the Covid-19 pandemic. Teachers accepted the situation of working from home because of the health crises. Valuable lessons such as using technology-induced learning materials while teaching online, understanding learners, especially during this pandemic, emerged for teachers who are working at home and assuring to know the learners well in the new learning platform. Further, a positive feeling is just a matter of accepting the task given to you, making the most out of it, and enjoying the situation. A positive outlook among teachers amidst the COVID-19 pandemic is evident through stress, and anxiety is apparent in their lives. This is because they are not able to do the things that they once used to do as their lifestyle changed (Ballesteros, H., & Ocampo, K., 2016; Altena, E., Baglioni, C., Espie, C., Ellis, J., Gavriloff, D., Holzinger, B., & Riemann, D., 2020; 2020; Sepulveda-Escobar & Morrison, 2020; Talidong, K. J. B., & Toquero, 2020; Lepp, Aaviku, Leijen, Pedaste, & Saks, 2021).

“I have to feel positive since we are dealing with this pandemic situation. I have to respond or abide by the health protocols to be safe.” Participant 1, lines 26-28

“We must adjust ourselves so that it will not give us a negative impact on our work, so we can be as productive just like working at school.”

- Participant 1, lines 212-214

Table 2

The Thematic Analysis of the participants feeling on working from home during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Main Theme: The Ups and Downs of Productivity

Cluster Themes	Emergent Themes
1. Hesitation	1. Negative Feelings
2. Cluelessness	
3. Self-doubts	
4. Annoyance	
5. Sadness and disappointments	
6. Distraction	
7. Stressed	
8. Tiresome	
9. Happiness	2. Positive Feelings
10. Inspired	
11. Striving to teach and find new ways to connect with pupils	
12. Pride and accomplishments	

Main Theme: The Two-sides of Teaching Satisfaction

Positive Impacts

A teacher working from home should possess time management to maximize the flexible working hours while assuming parental duties at home. Working from home is a new set-up that needs a new approach. Teaching is a profession that needs unending training to achieve productivity. The teacher is the medium that realizes the objectives and plans of the Department of Education (Medina, 2016; Khan, Farooqi, Khalil, & Faisal, 2016; Gepila, Rural, Lavadia, Nero, Palillo & Besmonte, 2018; Bautista, S., 2020; Department of Education, 2020; Ranjha, F., Pasha, S., & Shah, S., 2021). For this reason, the teacher must have an outstanding job satisfaction level that leads to his performance. Working from home had two-sided effects among teachers, as they tried to cope with the fast-changing educational landscape.

“Kinahanglan nako dawaton nga mao na ni ang bag-o or ginatawag nato nga new normal ug safe sad sa tanan ang pag work from home. Buhaton nako akong best para magampanan ako trabaho as a teacher sa bag-o na nato nga sitwasyon.” (I have to accept the fact that this is the new normal and it is the safety of everybody to work from home. I will do my best to do my task as teacher in this new situation” - Participant 2, lines 396-399

“So that I had nothing to worry about. In this way, I’m motivated to do my work.” - Participant 2, lines 415-416

“Well, we have no choice because it’s our job, I will do my responsibility since this is what they called the new normal. We are instructed to work from home, so we must work at home. That’s it.” - Participant 3, lines 533-535

Negative Impacts

Time is a significant factor in working from home. Making school reports, collating modules, checking pupils’ performance, monitoring pupils’ progress, and other concerns require effort and time. Participants experienced checking self-learning modules late at night and submitting reports because of their home situation that consumes most of their time and energy. Demands on teachers’ time require well-developed organizational skills. It was found out that most teachers had been trained to work in monograde classrooms before the Covid-19 pandemic. It was also concluded that knowledge of teaching is based on whole-class instruction. Teachers recognized that the time commitments and abilities required to be effective in a work-from-home environment were not part of their past training and experience (Espinosa, B., 2016; Divina, 2017; Kintanar, M., 2017; Delapeña, M., 2020).

“As for me, maybe I may not work productively because my focus was divided between myself and my learner’s situation.” - Participant 1, lines 107-108

“I am not motivated to work at home.” - Participant 2, line 305

“These emotions make me less productive as a teacher, we cannot expect a good quality of work when you are lonely, stressed, and unmotivated. - Participant 2, lines 345-347

“Yes, again I am less motivated because maybe as I said because of the atmosphere at home compared to the atmosphere at school.” - Participant 2, lines 382-383

“You left your work unfinished because you are at home, your responsibilities at home was the first priority. You can say I will work it out later, and do your household work first.- Participant 3, lines 603-605

Table 3
The Thematic Analysis of the Effects of Working from Home among Teachers

Main Theme: The Two-sides of Teaching Satisfaction

Cluster Themes	Emergent Themes
1. Cannot monitor concrete progress of all learners	1. Negative Impacts
2. Insufficient time to collate and prepare self-learning modules	
3. Late in accomplishing online school reports	
4. Stressed	
5. Some modules are lacking	
6. Utilizing flexible work hours	2. Positive Impacts
7. Developing patience	
8. Motivated to teach	
9. Goal-oriented	
10. Felt safe and secure	

This qualitative research describes the impact of work from home among teachers in Saavedra Saway Central Elementary School, Labangal District, Division of General Santos City and is categorized into three main themes: The Challenge of Connectivity, The Ups and Down of Productivity, and The Two-sides of Teaching Satisfaction. Teacher participants have the same idea of how working from home in an actual situation operates. They perceived that the impact of work from home during the Covid-19 is the challenge for connectivity, the ups and downs of productivity, and the two sides of teaching satisfaction. They claimed that internet connectivity is the most significant challenge in working from home. The participants share the positive and negative impacts of work from home. Work from home activities is more adaptable in completing work; for those who work day by day before a portable workstation, it is sure to have an uncommon work area and chair as their working environment. There are times when teachers feel bored and require a new working environment. For this reason, it isn't unprecedented for various public schools to provide new places within the office to maximize instructional delivery. Similarly, when Working from Home, the teacher can work anywhere from home, from their living room, bedroom, dining room, outdoor garden, and so on.

The teacher can also assess his degree of comfort at work. Importantly, when working from home, the instructor has complete control over the job to be completed that day, as seen and understood by teacher participants. One of the significant advantages of Work From Home, as reflected by participants in this study is that, teachers do not need to follow the rigorous office hours at school. Furthermore, in Working From Home, teachers don't have to spend too much money to pay for transportation or gas costs; teachers can also save travel time from the workstation, thus, maximizing outputs. For teachers living in a highly urbanized city, who are also often stuck in traffic jams on the road to school, these teachers make the most of Work from Home benefits. Moreover, by working from home, teacher participants minimize the level of stress experienced. In addition to traffic jams from home to their workstation, one of the reasons that usually trigger anxiety among teachers is the accumulation of work. Teachers who manage their time well did not perceive Work from Home as a problem. When teachers do not feel stressed in their job, of course, their productivity will increase. That way, teachers get the job done so quickly. Once teachers complete their work faster and more effectively, job satisfaction will follow. When teachers can finish the job well for the day, of course, they tend to feel more excited the next. Teachers'

job satisfaction will certainly further increase their productivity; those are the ups of work from home to teacher's productivity. The many demands of the Department of Education during the Covid-19 pandemic sometimes force teachers to lose their balance between work and family life.

Moreover, with the Work from Home alternative arrangement in public schools, teachers can more easily divide their role. There are times when teachers focus on school hours, and at times they can still carry out their family roles without any burden. Another advantage of Work from Home those teachers feel is that they have more free time with their families. Teachers can make a more secure, comfortable, and conducive atmosphere for their families when working at home. On the other hand, one of the disadvantages of Work from Home is that teachers can lose work motivation. The reasons are pretty more diverse among participants. For example, the working atmosphere is not what teachers expect, the house's atmosphere is not like a classroom, teachers are usually distracted by social media and other entertainment, etc. When losing positive motivation to work, the teachers typically rest and do not push themselves to their limits. If teachers move too far, the mood for work will increasingly disappear. When working in a classroom, the school bears the cost of electricity and the internet.

However, when teachers are working from home, things are different since their power and internet expenses may rise due to their continued use. To lessen the disadvantages of this Work from Home, teachers indeed have a special allowance intended for the purpose. There is an alarming rise of data security issues in using internet access in public areas. Teachers are not usually aware of this; they should not provide e-mail addresses or cellphone numbers when they access free public Wi-Fi because it can cause data security issues. When Working from Home, teachers rely heavily on technology to communicate with other co-teachers. Many people doubted the effectiveness of work from home; the alternative work arrangement for Work from Home is considered the most viable work order during the Covid-19 pandemic. Because, in addition to helping the government efforts minimize the risk of Coronavirus transmission, Work from Home also help ensure that schools and public education continue to run well. A precise Work From Home procedure will motivate teachers to commit themselves wholeheartedly to the Department of Education's long-term goals, even when not in the classroom. There are roadblocks in every endeavor, like what teacher participants in Saavedra Saway Central Elementary School encountered. The participants had difficulty in internet connection and combining teaching work with responsibilities at home. As to the challenging experience of teachers in working from home, the teacher participants felt the challenge in online connectivity and maximizing productivity with the flexible working hours they had while feeling motivated by their family at home. Moreover, participants articulated that working from home needs time management skills to make them productive teachers during the Covid-19 pandemic; teacher participants are reflective of their performance, sensitive to learners' needs in the new educational landscape, task-oriented, and goal-oriented. This only shows that it brings sound effects to teachers' performance. On the other hand, the teacher participants expressed their need for a strong internet connection and prepaid load while working from home to enhance the essential services that DepEd expects them to carry out despite the pandemic.

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